

PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DOUBLE YARN PRODUCED FROM A COTTON/POLYESTER BLEND

Ro'zibayev Nuriddin Nurali o'g'li

Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry.

PhD Associate Professor

Тел: +998974859393.

E-mail:nuriddinroziboev5@gmail.com

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Abstract.

The article provides a detailed analysis of known methods for producing yarn from mixed fibers with varying densities. Based on the analysis of existing methods for obtaining composite yarn from blended cotton and viscose fibers, cotton and polyester, as well as cotton fibers and bamboo. The technology and equipment used to produce the recommended yarn for these three variants are presented. Their comparative qualitative characteristics are provided.

Аннотация.

В статье приводится подробный анализ известных способов получения пряжи из смешанных волокон с различной плотностью. На основе анализа существующих способов получения композиционной пряжи из смешанных волокон хлопка и вискозы, из хлопка и полиэстера. Приводятся технология и используемое оборудование для получения рекомендуемой пряжи для трех вариантов. Представлены их сравнительные качественные характеристики.

Ключевые слова

Пряжа, композиционный, волокна, смешанный, ровница, хлопок полиакрилонитрил, полиэфир, вискоза, полиэстер, бамбук, удлинение, разрывная нагрузка, прочность, текс, уплотнитель, элемент сохранителей крутки

Keywords

Yarn, composite, fibers, mixed, roving, cotton, polyacrylonitrile, polyester, viscose, polyester, bamboo, elongation, tensile strength, strength, tex, sealant, twist retainer element

Introduction.

Globally, the textile industry plays a key role in the economy, holding a leading position in the processing of natural and synthetic fibers, as well as in providing the population and industry with necessary products. This contributes to the growth of yarn production volumes. According to the data, the global

production of finished garments and knitwear reaches 120 billion units, with the main centers of production remaining the countries of East and South Asia, the USA, Europe, and the CIS. In these conditions, it is important to effectively use ring spinning machines to produce high-quality and competitive yarn necessary for the textile industry. In this regard, the use of modern, energy-efficient equipment is becoming a key factor in the development of new types of yarn.

The development of regulatory technological parameters that positively influence the yarn production process, as well as the creation of new spinning techniques and technologies, is of particular importance. Research on the production of blended double yarn is considered a priority in this area. In the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, important tasks have been identified: increasing the volume of industrial production by 1.4 times by continuing the industrial policy aimed at ensuring the stability of the national economy and increasing the share of industry in the gross domestic product. Within the framework of the implementation of these tasks, including in the concept for the development of the textile and knitwear industry, priority areas have been identified: improving technologies, saving raw materials and supplies, creating new high-performance equipment, and introducing automated electronic control systems into production processes. This will significantly increase the efficiency of blended fabric production. Special attention is being paid to improving the technology for obtaining blended yarn used in knitted fabrics, particularly focusing on the production of plied yarn and enhancing the competitiveness of products in the global market.

Research in this area shows that multicomponent double yarn with medium and high linear density was mainly produced from fine-fiber cotton, wool, and chemical fibers. The production of multicomponent doubled yarn with an average linear density from a mixture of medium-staple cotton fiber with a length of 35mm grown in our Republic and polyester fiber has not been sufficiently studied.

In global spinning production, methods for obtaining yarn by mixing various artificial and natural fibers are increasingly emerging [1,2,3,4].

Development of a method for producing yarn from mixed fibers. To obtain composite yarn from blended fibers, ensuring a technical result that expands the range of blended yarn with improved tensile characteristics, quality, and consumer properties, while effectively using artificial and natural fibers, new fiber components are recommended.

The method involves producing composite yarn from blended fibers with average linear density of type IV 1st and 2nd grade cotton fibers mixed with

chemical fibers, such as cotton-bamboo (50/50), cotton-viscose (50/50), and cotton-polyester (50/50) on a ring spinning machine, resulting in doubled yarn (29 tex) [5]. The recommended composite yarn is obtained by mixing cotton fibers and chemical fibers in the following proportions for three variants:

- cotton fiber 50%; viscose 50%;
- cotton fiber 50%; polyester 50%;

In this case, in all three variants, the fiber length is selected within the range of 35 mm (average value of cotton fibers). Obtaining composite yarn for all three variants is carried out on the Zinser 351 spinning machine. At the same time, doubled yarn of 29 tex with improved characteristics was obtained.

The influence of the distance between the intermediate openings of the roving compactors on the twist triangle during the production of plied yarn by the spinning-twisting method is clearly shown in Figure 1.

Таблица-1

Physical and mechanical indicators of doubled yarn obtained from a mixture of cotton/polyester fibers

№	Наименование показателей	Options for spacing between intermediate holes of roving seals		
		8 мм	10 мм	12 мм
1	Linear yarn density, teks	29	29	29
2	Coefficient of variation for linear density, %	0,96	1,27	1,55
3	Breaking strength; cN	18		
4	Relative breaking strength, cN/teks	18,95	1	,
5	Coefficient of variation for relative breaking load, %	,04		4
6	Elongation	%	9,14	9
		См		
7	Breaking strength, (kg/cm)	0,5	0,53	0,55
8	Relative breaking work per 1 g of yarn	3	3	3

Figure 1 - Indicators of the physical and mechanical properties of yarn

- relative breaking strength of yarn, cN/tex
- coefficient of variation for relative breaking strength, %
- elongation at break, %

In Figure 1, the relative breaking load of yarn passing through the KS seal is 18.95-19.54 cN/tex. In the comparative variants, when using KN8 seals, the tensile strength is 18.65-18.94 cN/tex, and when using KN4 seals, the tensile strength is within the range of 18.35-18.64. cN/tex.

When using KS compactors, the yarn elongation at break was KN12 9.14-9.35%, when using KN8 compactor - 8.94-9.25%, and when using KN10 compactor - 8.84-9.15%, i.e., the highest indicators of yarn elongation at break were observed in variants 1,2,3 when using KS compactors.

In yarn production technology, high elongation is of great importance, as the yarn first stretches to a certain degree, after which stress occurs under its influence.

Conclusions. Based on the analysis of existing methods for obtaining yarn from blended fibers, a method for obtaining yarn with improved characteristics was recommended: a) cotton fiber - 50% and viscose - 50%; b) cotton fiber - 50% and polyester - 50%. Based on the analysis of the influence of the seals on the quality indicators of the yarn, the KS sealer was recommended.

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